

SUSTAINABLE ALTERNATIVES FOR AN URBAN PARK FROM THE SOUND ASSESSMENT

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ABSTRACT

Noise pollution is one of the current problems that deteriorate the quality of life and productivity of the inhabitants in an urban or rural environment. In most cases, determined by the various activities of the habitat. One of the strategies for mitigating the noise produced is green spaces. They play an important role in our health and constitute positive scenarios that favor social encounters, promote cultural diversity and generate symbolic values of identity and belonging to citizens. The objective of this work is to quantify, identify and evaluate the acoustic behavior of a public green space of great importance in the city of San Miguel de Tucumán, through the study of certain variables and sound, environmental and social indicators. The exploratory and descriptive, analytical-deductive methods and the case study were adopted. Quantitative and qualitative paradigms were used through survey and sound measurements in 13 determined points in the sector, with instruments according to IRAM Standards and surveys of users of said spaces. It was observed that the noise levels obtained from the measurements in the interior of the park were lower than those obtained in the exterior points, and perhaps the vegetation could influence these results. However, they were higher than those recommended by the World Health Organization (WHO) of 55 dB (A). Based on this, sustainable technological solutions are proposed made with vegetation and waste materials from construction works that allow achieving a reduction in sound levels.

KEYWORDS

Habitat, Noise pollution, Urban park, Sustainable technologies.

INTRODUCTION

The area selected for this work is a public green space located on an important avenue in the city, where thousands of people, medium and long distance buses, vehicles and heavy load transports pass daily. In this urban road, there is a residential area, an important commercial sector, a private sanatorium, service stations and a park with important dimensions and a great contribution of vegetation.

The idea of green spaces is closely linked to the principle of quality of life and well-being offered by vegetation, a central element in all urban planning. In this line, Capel (2002) writes: "The concept of Public Parks was introduced at the beginning of the 19th century as an initial response to the environmental problems that arose in European cities, where, due to the Industrial Revolution, the pace of growth began to affect the health conditions of their inhabitants and, in addition, their quality of life,

which in some way led to reflection on the disadvantages and consequences of urban development without planning.

According to Tella and Potocko (2009), they consider that: "There are three major categories of public green spaces: There are the sites and areas that define the city landscape, where the elements of the topography assume an exceptional value by defining the natural landscape and structuring urban uses, then the Parks and Walks, open spaces of the city, of special dimensions and landscape characteristics and whose collective use is mainly intended for recreational activities and finally there are the streets of the urban layout that by their dimensions, traffic, uses and trees, constitute axes of singular value".

A study conducted by the World Health Organization (WHO, 2011) estimates that each person should have 10 to 15 square meters of green space to live in a healthy environment, considering that figure as an indicator of urban quality of life. In the particular case of the city of San Miguel de Tucumán, there are approximately 5.8 square meters of green space per inhabitant.

From the conception of the city and the ways of inhabiting the place, the complexity of soundspace is observed as an important sensory component that reveals the relationship of urban dwellers with their outside world (Agnew, 2011; Simmel, 1998). A soundscape encompasses the sounds, or sonic energy, produced by specific places or landscapes (Farina, 2014; Miller, 2013). That is, soundscape is the set of sounds of the environment that accompany a certain environment, which have their own identity and are inseparable from different circumstances, place, time or certain activity. Therefore, the sound environment, which is the sum of the totality of sounds within a defined area, is an intimate reflection of the social, political, technological and natural conditions of the area.

The objective of this work is to characterize and analyze the levels of noise pollution in the park under study, and to identify the different types of soundscapes found in it. To this end, the aim is to study the existing noise by means of sound measurements taken with instruments according to regulations at 13 points in the park, from which different acoustic indicators have been calculated. Likewise, a study has been carried out to evaluate the acoustic perception by users and visitors, seeking to identify the variables that interfere in this urban space and to interrelate the objective and subjective indicators that can characterize the soundscape.

To this end, sustainable technological-architectural solutions are proposed for the acoustic adaptation of these public green spaces, in order to achieve Acoustic Quality of the different areas evaluated.

METHODOLOGY

This work was developed through a methodological combination, which is framed within Participatory Action Research. The research was approached in stages, with the objective of analyzing, evaluating and characterizing the sound environment of an urban park within the municipality of San Miguel de Tucumán. On the one hand, a quantitative analysis was carried out by characterizing the physical conditions of urban environments and measuring noise levels; and, on the other hand, a qualitative analysis was carried out by learning about the problem from the perception of the users who live in and/or walk through the park.

In the first stage, urban profiles were elaborated as descriptive instruments for comparison and evaluation of the physical conditions of the sector. In the second stage, a quantitative analysis was carried out by means of sound measurements with a standard instrument. In the third stage, the qualitative method was used, by means of user surveys. The data obtained were systematized and synthesized through tables and graphs.

Urban park analyzed

The city of San Miguel de Tucumán is the capital of the province of Tucumán, considered the metropolis of the Norte Grande Argentino Region and the fifth largest city in the country. The case study is the Parque El Provincial, located towards the south of the city, recently refunctionalized in its 3 sectors.

Figure 1: Location of El Provincial Park, Tucumán-Argentina.

The park is located on Roca Avenue at 500, and is developed in three blocks on the same avenue, with an area of 42,737.51 m². These blocks are integrated to the grid and are linked through the avenue, in an area of intense vehicular traffic, which gives this sector a commercial as well as residential character. Its limiting streets are between 9 de Julio Street to the east, Ayacucho Street to the west and Alsina Street to the south.

It became the first experience in the capital with enclosed green spaces. Despite the fences around each block, the spatial approximation of these makes it a continuous park, as a whole and not as three separate parks. At the same time, it harmonizes with the context of the schools located on the same property, by continuing with the morphology of an enclosed space towards the municipal line. The walkways were designed according to the location of the existing trees.

From a social perspective, the urban conditions of recovering spaces for the city, favors the social encounter, offers necessary spaces to carry out positive activities for human development (sports, culture, recreation); and generates in the public space an action that positively favors the behavior of those who live in that territory.

The park has 3 urban blocks, in which 13 strategic points were determined that allowed to characterize and know the acoustic conditions of the chosen sectors.

Figure 2: El Provincial Park with the points analyzed in each sector.

Methodological tools used

The analytical and deductive methods were used to evaluate the environmental noise indicators. In the first instance, with a quantitative analysis, sound level measurements were taken with instruments according to the recommendations of the IRAM 4113 NORM: "Acoustics. Description, measurement and evaluation of environmental noise".

IRAM 4113-1/2009: Part 1 - Basic magnitudes and evaluation methods.
IRAM 4113-2/2010: Part 2 - Determination of environmental noise levels.

The measurements, based on the specifications of the standard, were performed according to the following acoustic parameters:

- **Instrumentation:** a Lutron brand Integrating Digital Sound Level Meter (Integrating Sound Level Meter SL-4035SD) class 2. Frequency and time weighting designed to comply with IEC 61672 class 2 standards;

- It has a standard 0.5" microphone head, with extreme sensitivity, omnidirectional that allows picking up sound from various directions. Built-in windshield, with the purpose of avoiding a fictitious increase of the measured levels;

- The microphone was held at a height of 1.20 meters with the equipment located on the sidewalk and 1 meter away from the street, with the microphone directed towards the opposite sidewalk. It was ensured that the location of the instrumentation corresponded to sidewalks free of objects that could interfere with the measurement, such as parked vehicles, advertising signs, traffic signals, etc.

- Stores readings in SD type external memory: A memory card was used to record the values in a Microsoft Excel spreadsheet software; it includes a clock with calendar, real time recording, with a Fast frequency of 125 ms.

- The survey was carried out during daylight hours on the same day, between 11:00 a.m. and 2:00 p.m., with a duration of 5 to 8 minutes at each selected point.

Figure 3: Measurements with instruments according to regulations.

- **Equivalent Continuous Sound Level (LAeq):** It is an indicator that allows describing noise pollution in a location. It shows the noise level accumulated over a period of time and standardized with respect to that interval.

- **Percentile levels L10 and L90:** The percentiles indicate the noise level that is exceeded in a certain percentage of the measurement time. The smaller the percentage of time, the higher the noise level to be exceeded. The L90 percentile defines the sound level that has been exceeded during 90% of the measurement time and is usually used for the measurement of background noise levels. In contrast, the L10 value is the level that has just been exceeded for 10% of the time and takes into account annoying noise peaks.

For the qualitative assessment, a short survey was used, which was carried out on passers-by or users walking through the area under consideration. These were carried out simultaneously with the acoustic measurements, to randomly selected groups of people. This is one of the most widely used subjective methods to assess certain conditions or situations based on the opinion of those affected.

In this work, the socio-acoustic survey tool is applied on site, in order to know the effects of noise in the urban green space, as perceived by the people who live and/or go to the area on a daily basis. These contained closed questions and multiple-choice questions, where the aim was to evaluate the perception of environmental noise and the annoyance produced by it. It is of great importance to know the subjective opinion of the people who are in direct and constant contact with the sounds of this area of the city. The questions were grouped into three sections: about the place of residence, knowledge about

noise pollution and the characteristics of existing urban noise. The data obtained were systematized and synthesized through tables and percentage graphs.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Objective evaluations are carried out with standard instruments at the selected points. Then, using spreadsheets, the data are transferred to sound level graphs.

Sector 1 West of the Park

This sector is bounded by Roca Avenue to the north, Chacabuco Street to the east, Alsina Street to the south and Ayacucho Street to the west. This block borders the "Próspero García" school for people with acoustic disabilities and a kindergarten.

Table 1: Sound measurement values.

NP	Urban Profiles	Sound level graphs	Values (dBA)
Point 1			Leq 64,2 dBA
			L10 67,3 dBA
			L90 55,5 dBA
Point 2			Leq 74,9 dBA
			L10 78,7 dBA
			L90 62,3 dBA
Point 3			Leq 61,9 dBA
			L10 65,1 dBA
			L90 54,5 dBA
Point 4			Leq 70,9 dBA
			L10 75,7 dBA
			L90 57,2 dBA
Point 5			Leq 67,8 dBA
			L10 73,7 dBA
			L90 55,2 dBA

Sector 2 Park Center

Bounded by Roca Avenue to the north, Buenos Aires Street to the east, Alsina Street to the south and Chacabuco Street to the west. This central block also houses the former railway station, whose building was remodeled and refunctionalized.

Table 2: Sound measurement values.

NP	Urban Profiles	Sound level graphs	Values (dBA)
Point 6			Leq 66 dBA
			L10 69,7 dBA
			L90 55,6 dBA
Point 7			Leq 57,2 dBA
			L10 58,9 dBA
			L90 54,3 dBA
Point 8			Leq 76,2 dBA
			L10 79,8 dBA
			L90 60,9 dBA
Point 9			Leq 71 dBA
			L10 76,1 dBA
			L90 58,1 dBA

Sector 3 East of the Park

Bounded by Roca Avenue to the north, Buenos Aires Street to the east, Alsina Street to the south and 99 de Julio Street to the west. The block to the east adjoins the "Luis Braille" school for the visually impaired.

Table 3: Sound measurement values.

NP	Urban Profiles	Sound level graphs	Values (dBA)
Point 10			Leq 66,8 dBA
			L10 71,5 dBA
			L90 52,5 dBA
Point 11			Leq 69,3 dBA
			L10 73,9 dBA
			L90 56,8 dBA

The first part of the evaluation is carried out by preparing urban profiles for each point to characterize the sector. Sidewalk widths, distances between roadways, façade heights of immediate buildings and vegetation were taken into account.

PROPOSALS FOR ACOUSTIC IMPROVEMENT

Based on the results obtained, sustainable technological-architectural proposals are made to allow a sound adaptation in the analyzed site and, at the same time, to prevent the park itself from being a disturbing sound source to its soundscape.

This park was put into operation by the municipality of San Miguel de Tucumán since it was out of use and formed an urban void, generating unsafe and impassable areas. It is also the first enclosed public park with perimeter fences in the province.

In order to support the avant-garde stamp that these constructions represent on the municipal line in a public green space, a series of proposals of screens that improve both visually and acoustically the case of analysis are projected.

Acoustic acrylic screens: made with flat extruded acrylic sheet.

This is the placement of a system of screens on the perimeter railings that serve the function of being sound-absorbing and insulating. It also serves to reinforce the idea of the park and its aesthetics, allowing visuals towards the interior of the park and in relation to its context.

Regarding acoustic performance: the resonance frequency of the complex is 27240.82 Hz and the acoustic reduction is 42 dB. With a sound intensity level outside the park of 76.2 dBA, inside the park, it reaches an interior AQL of 34.2 dBA, complying with the permissible background noise level for open public spaces of 35 dBA.

Figure 4: detail of the proposed acoustic screens.

Characteristics of the acoustic screen system:
Acoustic barrier for protection against high traffic.

Light weight, high clarity material. Transparent, up to 92% light transmission.
 Good thermal insulator.
 Good chemical resistance.

Figure 5: Views of the proposed acoustic screens.

Green screens: made with vegetation and waste materials from construction sites.

Alternative to the acrylic screen, designed with the possibility of the acoustic barrier being covered by climbing species planted at the foot of the screen, and growing upwards using the galvanized steel mesh as a support. They also serve to reinforce the idea of the park and its aesthetics with the use of vegetation.

It consists of a standardized metallic structure with a modular adjustment system and exterior cladding with multi-perforated sheet metal. It contains in its interior high-density mineral rock wool that absorbs ambient noise and also serves as a highly effective barrier against noise.

Figure 6: detail of the proposed green screens.

Characteristics of the green screen system:

100% flame retardant high density mineral rock wool with protective veil.

Totally suitable for outdoor use.

Dimensions: 1,20m x 0,90m (each module), and thickness of 0,13m.

Figure 7: Views of the proposed acoustic screens.

Absorbent materials for picnic areas

It is proposed to place elastic rubber pavements in picnic areas to reduce the impact noise generated by people and to attenuate noise pollution inside them.

Figure 8: detail of the proposed materials.

Characteristics

Thickness of 4cm, black surface finish.
 Permeable material that allows noise absorption.
 Reduces sound impact by 45%.

Figure 9: views of the proposed acoustic screens.

Absorbent materials for children's play area

It is proposed to place colored poured-in-place rubber flooring in the children's play areas to reduce impact noise generated by infants and to reduce noise pollution in the park.

Figure 10: detail of the proposed materials.

Features

Meets safety standards for playground surfacing.
 Reduces maintenance costs.
 Raw material from recycled products.
 Draining pavement, suitable for outdoors.
 Reduces noise impact by 45%.

Figure 11: Views of the proposed acoustic screens.

CONCLUSION

The resulting noises that we perceive are often perfectly avoidable if the producers who generate them are made aware of them and if they are properly controlled.

Public green spaces are one of the main articulators of social life. They are places for meeting, integration and exchange; they promote the cultural and generational diversity of a society; and they generate symbolic value, identity and belonging. Intervention in public space implies an improvement in the urban image.

In a series of sound measurements with standardized instruments according to IRAM 4062 standards, it was observed that the park had the lowest urban noise values of those analyzed (evaluation made on Roca Avenue), so the influence of vegetation could be significant for the results obtained.

The safeguarding, revitalization, regeneration and dissemination of the intangible cultural heritage of each community will be a factor that will contribute decisively to the valuation and conservation of regional and local cultures. A soundscape is an environment where the most important thing is the way it is perceived and interpreted by the individual or society and its identity.

The areas near the park have the lowest sound levels, making them ideal resting areas for users. Therefore, the presence of vegetation along the different surrounding urban axes can generate great environmental and social benefits, including noise mitigation, which depends on the characteristics, structure and density of the vegetation.

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare that they have no conflicts of interest associated with the work presented in this paper.

DATA AVAILABILITY

All necessary data is presented in this paper.